

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS AFFECTING USE OF TRADITIONAL MEDICINE AMONG PREGNANT WOMEN IN A RURAL COMMUNITY OF EBONYI STATE

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Abstract

Background: *The use of traditional medicine has been on the increase despite advances in orthodox medicine. Many rural dwellers depend solely on traditional healing systems for their health care. This study examines the socio-demographic factors that affect use of traditional medicine among pregnant women in a rural community in Ebonyi State.*

Methodology: *This was a cross sectional survey. Cochran sample size formula was used to determine the sample size; while simple random sampling was used to select the respondents respondent. Data was collected using questionnaire*

Results: *Majority of the respondents were less than 25 years of age. The median age 27 years. Similarly, majority of the respondents had primary education as their highest educational qualification. There is a very high usage of traditional medicine with 67%. Socio-demographic characteristics that were significant in predicting the likelihood of use of traditional medicine were age, educational qualification and income.*

Conclusion: *The use of traditional medicine was very high. The study therefore recommends awareness creation, and women empowerment such as free and compulsory education.*

Keywords

*Traditional medicine,
pregnant women, Ndufu-
Alike Ikwo, Ebonyi*

1. Introduction

Traditional medicine has a long history of use in health maintenance, diseases prevention and treatment; and it has been integrated into the culture of the people (1, 2). It is the indigenous system of health care in most Nigerian communities. As a result, many people are naturally prone to use of traditional medicine in many health conditions, including pregnancy and childcare [3, 4]. Although there has been tremendous advancement and development in orthodox medicine, the use of traditional medicine has continued to

persist (5). All over the world, many women use traditional medicine during pregnancy. Women use herbal medicine in almost all phases of their life cycle, from the menarche to menopause (6). The use of herbal medicine among women during pregnancy includes but not limited to the following reasons: twinge/pain, dermal problems, labour related reasons such as enhancing and/or inducing labour (7). The incidence of traditional medicine use in pregnancy in United Kingdom was (58%) [8], 51.4% in tumpat Malaysia [9]. Use of traditional medicines has been found to be on the increase in recent times (10, 11). Globally, use of herbal medicine had been in the increase (12, 13, and 14). It is estimated that about 80% to 95% of people living in Africa and other developing countries use traditional medicine in managing diseases (12, 13, 14).

The use of herbs and other healing practices that are aboriginal to the people in care and management of diverse health related problem is widespread in Nigeria (1, 15, 16, 17, 18, and 19). Traditional medicine is the foremost form of health care system for many. It is utilized basically for healing purposes. This could be due to its closeness to nature, affordability, availability, acceptability and its potency and efficacy in the treatment and cure of many health problems (20, 18).

The continued increase in maternal deaths is a pointer that many women particularly those in the rural areas, do not access and utilize adequate reproductive health care services especially during pregnancy (21).

The paper therefore examines the socio-demographic and economic factors affecting use of traditional medicine during pregnancy in a rural community of Ebonyi State.

2. Methods

The study was conducted in Ndufu-Alike community in Ikwo, Ebonyi State. Ikwo is one of the local government areas (LGA) in the state. It is one of the LGAs in the Ebonyi Central Senatorial zone. It shares border with cross river state, Abakaliki and Ezza local government area of Ebonyi state. It has a land mass of approximately 500 kilometers. The people of Ikwo are mostly farmers. Rice, yams, and cassava are the most popular crops they produce. They are considered the largest producers of Abakaliki rice in the State and are blessed with natural resources which include; lime, stones, lead, zinc, and salt deposited in various parts of the community. Ndufu-Alike is one of the communities in Ikwo, it is the community where Alex Ekwueme federal university is situated. Cross sectional survey was adopted as the study design. Cochran's sample size formula for unknown sample size was used [$n = Z^2 P (1-P) / d^2$]. A total of 384 respondents were used for the sample size. The study population was pregnant women and women with infants. House hold screening was used to identify household where pregnant or nursing mother lives. This formed a sampling frame while simple random sampling was used to select respondents. Data was collected using structured questionnaire that was researcher administered, IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 was used to analyse the data. Descriptive statistics such as simple percentages and cross tabulations were used; logistic regression was also used to make some predictions. The questionnaire was designed in a manner that it would not offend the respondents and they were not required to write their names. The purpose of the research was clearly explained to them, how and why they should participate was made clear to respondents, above all, they informed that they are free not to answer any questions they do not want to answer and to stop at any time they feel to do so without any attendant consequences.

3. Results

Table below displays the socio-economic and demographic characteristics of the respondents. Panel 1 shows that most of the respondents were less than 25 years of age with 31.3% belonging to this category. The next category was those in the age category 25-29 year with 21.1%. The median age was 27 years. Panel 2 shows that the majority of the respondents have primary education with 36.7%. This is followed by those with secondary education with 21.4%. Next were those with no formal education, this category had 16.9%. The occupational distribution shows that 53.9% were self-employed. These are those who are into all forms of self-employed enterprises such as trading, farming, fashion designing, hair dressing, and event planning among others. This is followed by those who were employed with 38.8%.

Marital status of the respondents shows that 47.9% were married while 38.3% were single; and 13.8% were formerly married. These were those who were widowed, separated or divorced.

Panel 5 shows that above half of the respondents reported a monthly income of less than ₦20,000:00 with 57.8%. About 19.3% of the respondents reported monthly income of less than ₦20,001-₦30,000:00, while 5.5% had a monthly income of above ₦50,001. With respect to religion, expectedly almost all the respondents were Christians, with 96.9%. Only 3.1% were African traditional religion. No respondent reported being a Muslim.

Table.1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents.

Panel	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1.	<u>Age:</u> <25 years 25-29 years 30-34 years 35-39 years 40-44 years 45 years+ Total	120 81 56 55 61 11 384	31.3 21.1 14.6 14.3 15.9 2.9 100.0
2.	<u>Education:</u> No formal education Primary education Secondary education NCE/OND/HND University Education Total	65 141 82 52 44 384	16.9 36.7 21.4 13.5 11.5 100.0
3	<u>Occupation:</u> Unemployed Employed Self employed Total	28 149 207 384	7.3 38.8 53.9 100.0
4.	<u>Marital Status:</u> Never married Married Formerly married Total	147 184 53 384	38.3 47.9 13.8 100.0
5	<u>Monthly Income:</u> Less ₦20,000 ₦20,001 - ₦30,000 ₦30,001 - ₦40,000 ₦40,001 - ₦50,000 Above ₦50,001 Total	222 74 39 28 21 384	57.8 19.3 10.2 7.3 5.5 100.0
6.	<u>Religion:</u> Christianity African Traditional Religion Total	372 12 384	96.9 3.1 100.0

The chart below is on the use traditional medicine during pregnancy. Close to two-third of the respondents (67%) use traditional medicine during pregnancy, while 33% do not use traditional medicine during pregnancy. This shows high level of traditional use among pregnant women in the study area

The table below is a logistic regression predicting the use of traditional medicine during by socio-demographic characteristics. Age, education and income were found to be significant predictors. Those in age bracket 30-34 years were 0.666 times more likely to use traditional medicine while those in ages 35-39 years were 0.168 times more likely to use traditional medicine.

Respondents who had primary education as their highest educational qualification were 0.099 times more likely to use traditional medicine, while those highest educational qualification is secondary education were 0.295 times more likely to use traditional medicine and those with NEC/OND/HND as their highest educational qualification were 0.039 times more likely to use traditional medicine.

Income was also found to be predictor of use of traditional medicine. Those whose income is less forty thousand naira were more likely to use traditional medicine. Respondents whose income was within ₦20,001 - ₦30,000 were 2.416 times more likely to use traditional medicine, while those whose income was within ₦30,001 - ₦40,000 were 1.005 times more likely to use traditional medicine.

Table 2. Socio-demographic predictors of traditional use during pregnancy

Variable	OR	95% CI	p-value
Age group			
≤25	1.000	-	-
25-29 years	1.003	0.486-2.068	0.859
30-34 years	0.666	0.313-1.416	0.007*
35-39 years	0.168	0.033-0.846	0.019*
40-44 years	0.238	0.067-0.977	0.673
Occupation			
Unemployed	1.000	-	-
Employed	0.177	0.313-1.416	0.617
Self employed	0.439	0.033-0.876	0.519
Marital status			
Never married	1.000	-	-
Married	8.459	3.002-23.833	0.756
Formerly married	1.049	0.476-2.064	0.632
Educational status			
No formal education	1.000	-	-

Primary education	0.099	0.026-0.375	0.000*
Secondary education	0.295	0.067-0.977	0.047*
NCE/OND/HND	0.039	0.011-0.136	0.000*
University Education	0.049	0.067-0.977	0.630
Monthly income			
Less ₦20,000	1.000	-	-
₦20,001 - ₦30,000	2.416	1.323-4.412	0.003*
₦30,001 - ₦40,000	1.005	0.486-2.178	0.000*
₦40,001 - ₦50,000	0.569	0.314-1.416	0.652
Above ₦50,001	0.179	0.073-0.846	0.670

*= significant at $P < .005$

4. Discussion

The study examined the socio-demographic factors affecting the use of traditional medicine among pregnant women in a rural community in Ebonyi State. There is high level of use of traditional medicine among the respondents (67%). This is quite high, and signifies dependence on nature and the traditional healing system which they are very familiar with. This is in line with the finding of 22 who found that 81.2% of the pregnant women she studied used traditional medicine during pregnancy.

Similarly, 13 in his study found that 74.5% of pregnant women use traditional medicine during pregnancy. It was also found that age of the respondents significantly predicts the likelihood of use of traditional medicine during pregnancy. Use of traditional medicine seems to be more at the late twenties and early thirties, as these age bracket were found to be significant in predicting the use of traditional medicine.

Earlier studies (1, 3, and 6) have found age to be a factor related to use of traditional medicine during pregnancy. This could be due to the fact that most of the respondents are young, and with primary education as the highest educational qualification; consequently they are still adhere and conform to their cultural beliefs and practices.

Related to the above, it is not surprising that the study revealed that educational qualification of the respondents significantly affect use of traditional medicine. This corroborates their findings of some scholars (1, 3, and 6) this could be due to their not being able to question some of their cultural beliefs and practices.

The last socio-demographic characteristic that is a predictor of the likelihood of using traditional medicine is income. This is for those whose income is less fifty thousand naira. However, for those whose income is above fifty thousand naira are not likely to use traditional medicine during pregnancy.

5. Conclusion

Use of traditional medicine is found to be high in this study. This could have some implications for the health of the fetus and the mother. Some socio-demographic characteristics like age, educational qualification, and income were found to be significant predictors of likelihood to use traditional medicine among pregnant women in the study area. The study therefore recommends awareness creation on the possible harm associated with the unregulated usage of traditional medicine. Government should make efforts to empower the people and give free and compulsory education from primary to University level as this will help reduce the age at which they give birth

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Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest in this study

Authors contribution**References**

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